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The Korean War in Indian Discourse: Memory,
Representation and Historical Consciousness

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1. Introduction

Korea and India has historical linkage since ancient time when Buddhism had played important role for cultural ties. There are several myths in both countries such as matrimonial relations between Korean Prince and Indian Princess. Both countries have faced colonial exploitation and freedom struggle for independence. Bilateral relations between India and Korea continued since centuries ago and in modern times both countries strengthened relations through various mechanism. In Post World War II, both countries had a lot in common. The end of World War II liberated both countries from the Colonial rule. It is wonderful fact that both countries won their independence from colonial rule on the 15th day of August.

After independence from colonial rule, both countries were divided into two nations. Pakistan was formed from India while Korea was divided into South Korea and North Korea. In this context, both countries have similar experienced for freedom struggle and division of nation. On the eve of World War II, the Western powers found it

difficult to come to an agreement regarding Korea. The USSR was in the northern part of Korea and quickly moving towards other parts of Korea. In this situation, the US had decided to compromise with the USSR for defeat of Japan. Both countries agreed that the USSR would be liberated the north part of Korea and the US in the south part of Korea from Japan. Japan was defeated by the allies power.

This paper is an attempt to examine the role of India in Korean war and its contribution to help Korea for making peace in peninsula from the perspective of Indian accounts. This paper uses primary and secondary sources for this purpose. The primary source of this paper is based on editorial articles of newspapers, official documents from various ministries of Korea that reflects Indian accounts of Korean war including report from India related to International institutions and autobiography. The secondary source is based on articles of journals, books and websites of government and non-government institutions. This paper is a tribute to the martyrs of Korean War.

2 India's Engagement in Korean War

India was involved in the Korean Question before the outbreak of the Korean War. India was involved in Korea through the United Nations Temporary Commission on Korea (UNTCOK) in 1947, which was conducting free and fair general election in Korea. UNTCOK chairman was KPS Menon who was Indian. India had not accepted the division of Korea into the North Korea and South Korea. According to India, the division of Korea was artificial. India believes after sometimes both countries would be united. India was active in breaking the deadlock between the USSR and the US in the United Nations to find a solution for Korean crisis. This was also a test of first Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru's idealistic foreign policy of non-alignment.

India become a member of the first United Nations Temporary Commission on Korea(UNTCOK), which was established on 14 November 1947. K.P.S. Menon of India was the common choice of both sides as the permanent chairman of the commission. The commission was established with a view to holding elections in both parts of Korea. It was required to act as a neutral observer of the elections and troop withdrawal and to report to the General Assembly. India was eager to perform duties in a fair and just manner and so on 14 January 1948, Mr. Menon gave a speech in which he said: The Thirty Eighth Parallel must be politically obliterated; it must be confined too the limbo of the past. We have come here with no political prejudices, no ideological predilections. The states we represent do not constitute a bloc.¹

He made it clear that the only aim of the commission was to see an independent and united Korea. Pointing out to the partition of India and its terrible after effects, he expressed hope that at least Korea would be spared this tragedy and would be unified, taking from both American and Russian systems that which suited best and would thus evolve a system of own in harmony with own traditions and culture.²

But in spite of India s best efforts, UNTCOK could not achieve the goal of the unification of Korea. Instead, it ended up holding elections only south of the 38th Parallel. This confirmed the division of the peninsula, creating on 15 August 1948.

¹ Menon, K. P. S. 1965, *Many Worlds: An Autobiography*, London: Oxford University Press, p 254, See also United Nations, 1948, First part of the report of the United Nations Temporary Commission on Korea. Volume II, annexes I-VIII, New York : Lake Success, p 06 & Yoon Sook Mo ed.1948, *Speeches of Dr. Menon- Chairman of UN Temporary Commission on Korea*, Seoul: Mun Hwa Dang, p 05 .

² Yoon Sook Mo ed.1948, *Speeches of Dr. Menon- Chairman of UN Temporary Commission on Korea*, Seoul: Mun Hwa Dang, pp7-8 See also United Nations, 1948, First part of the report of the United Nations Temporary Commission on Korea. Volume II, annexes I-VIII, New York : Lake Success, p 25 & 김경수,2006. 『인도와 한국전쟁 : 인도 비동맹외교의 기원』파주 : 한국학술정보 p 132.

India was against the North Korean aggression to South Korea. In this regard, India supported the United Nations' resolution to assist South Korea to stop the North Korean aggression. India also sent a medical mission to support the United Nations' operation in Korea. India sent the 60 Indian Field Ambulance Unit of the Army Medical Corps, consisting of 17 officers, 9 JCOs and 300 other ranks under the command of Lt. Col. A.G. Rangaraj.³

3. An Indian View of Korean War

This paper is an attempt to identify the foundations on which India viewed the Korean War through various Indian accounts such as autobiography, newspaper articles and scrapbooks. The written works of several Indians such as Col Manakampat Kesavan Unni Nair, Gen Brij Mohan Kaul, Lt Gen Ashoka Banerjee, Bhagwat Sharan Upadhyay and Jagat S Mehata among others provide the Indian view of the Korean war from the person who have directly experienced it in many ways. Further, these observations on Korean war have also proved to be the foundation of the perspective India has developed for the Korean problem historically.

3.1 Colonel Manakampat Kesavan Unni Nair and General Brij Mohan Kaul

Colonel Manakampat Kesavan Unni Nair was born on April 22, 1911. Being an adventurer, his daredevil acts in visiting disaster zones and reporting from Korea catapulted him to the top. The same trait proved his nemesis in South Korea.

He was later appointed as Public Relations Officer in Washington, a post which he held until his death in Korea when the jeep in which he was travelling exploded over a mine. A memorial has been established in his name in the National Press Club in Washington.⁴

Colonel M K Unni Nair was a commissioned officer in the Maratha Light Infantry, went to South Korea as part of a team of UN observers amid the Korean War. He died in a mine blast on August 12, 1950.⁵ The colonel's body could not be sent back to India amid the raging war. He was cremated in the hill range near Daegu. The provincial government built a memorial for the soldier on the site. The tribute is a national monument now. In 2003, the South Korean ministry declared this place a national monument.

Colonel M K Unni Nair travelled with the Indian Army to many places, including Italy. After Independence, he was appointed as an information officer of the armed forces. He continued to visit strife-torn areas to prepare official reports. He was serving as a public relations officer in the Indian embassy in Washington D C when the Korean War broke out.

Lt General Brij Mohan Kaul was an upright and straight forward General of the Indian Army. He resigned in 1963 in the aftermath of the Indian military debacle against the Chinese in the 1962 Sino-Indian War, becoming a fall guy of the skewed foreign policy of the Indian Government of the time. His autobiography "The Untold story" gives his six months experiences of Korea.

Here he recalls how the U N Command held 58,000 Chinese and North Korean prisoners in their custody and the Communists held, in turn, comparatively a very small number of British and American captives. According to the Western view, as the conditions in their homes under Communist rule were unbearable, none of the prisoners

³ Ministry of National Defence, History of UN Forces in Korean War, Seoul, 1973, Vol. II, p.468

⁴ Natarajan J. (1955) History of Indian Journalism Part ii of the report of the press commission, Delhi: Publications division Ministry of information and broadcasting Government of India ,p325.

⁵ Natarajan J. (1955) History of Indian Journalism Part ii of the report of the press commission, Delhi: Publications division Ministry of information and broadcasting Government of India p 325, also see 손규석, 조성훈, 김상원, 6.25 전쟁과 UN 군 , 서울 : 국방부 군사편찬연구소, 2015 p373, Also see Won, Tae-jae , The history of the nations that provided medical assistance in the Korean war : [Sweden, India, Denmark, Norway, Italy [translator, Changsu Kim] Sejong : Ministry of Patriots and Veterans Affairs, 2014. p 97 &p 116

wanted to be repatriated. The opposite view was that most prisoners, except perhaps a few, after a protracted separation from their families, and after fighting a relentless war, would be anxious to go back home. The Neutral Nations Repatriation Commission which was headed by him, was to determine from each prisoner whether he wished to be repatriated or go elsewhere. This account of Gen Brij Mohan Kaul also mentioned in Syngman Rhee's account and researched in detail also.⁶

3.2 Lt Gen K. S. Thimayya and Jagat S Mehta

Lt Gen K. S. Thimayya was chosen by India to represent as Chairman of the Neutral Nations Repatriation Commission (NNRC). Chakravarty went as the Alternate Chairman and P. N. Haksar along with Bahadur Singh, as political advisers. Lt Gen S. P. P. Thorat was to go as Commander of the Indian Custodian Force. Brij Mohan Kaul was nominated by Thimayya as his Chief of Staff.⁷

Gen. Kaul recalls his brief about POW situation in Korea with Prime minister Nehru and wrote:

Nehru sent for me before I left for Korea and explained various implications of the problem of prisoners of war confronting us then and how both USA and USSR were anxious to establish the rightness of their ideologies. They were bound to exert much pressure on us and it was, Nehru said, essential that we not only observed a strictly impartial attitude but also succeeded in giving an impression of doing so. As Chairman of the Commission, India would occupy a position of trust and must create a stabilising atmosphere of impartiality around ourselves in this combustible situation and thus reduce the tension which existed internationally. He suggested we made an initial gesture by sending a message of goodwill to all prisoners. We should try and learn the Korean language as it would give the impression of our interestedness in their problem. He said there might be some prisoners not willing to go home; we should, therefore, start with a batch appearing to be willing to do so. He felt that as most prisoners were ordinary peasants, free from politics, and hence naturally anxious to get back home, we should treat them sympathetically. He suggested we should segregate prisoners who were objectionable and watch for their ring leaders. We might find them reluctant to give details of their antecedents to the interrogators. They should, in that case, be persuaded to do so. Nehru finally said if there was a dead-lock in any situation, we should try and solve it informally.⁸

An insightful account of the events related to Korean war has been also provided by a former Indian foreign secretary (1976-79), Jagat S. Mehta, in his book *The Tryst Betrayed: Reflections on Diplomacy and Development*. Upon becoming deputy secretary (east) of the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) in 1956, Mehta realised that about 90 POWs had been in Delhi since 1954 and that they had largely been forgotten by the government. Mehta noted that upon reopening the files related to the POWs, the latter were given the choice of migrating to another country or staying on in India.

3.3 Bhagwat Sharan Upadhyay

⁶On the night of 18 June 1953, South Korean President Syngman Rhee released nearly 25,000 "non-repatriate" North Korean prisoners of war (pows). The event occurred just as United Nations Command (UNC), Chinese, and North Korean negotiators were preparing to sign a hard-fought armistice agreement at Panmunjom that long had been delayed on the question of voluntary repatriation of pows. UNC officials articulated an enduring tale of surprise and betrayal, one that persists in Korean War histories to this day. According to UNC POW camp records discovered that the U S Army, in fact, formulated a deliberate strategy of restraint for a likely prisoner release. This plan grew out of UNC Commander General Mark W. Clark's sympathy for anti-Communist pows and a sense of anxiety regarding the future of US relations with the Republic of Korea (ROK). For details See Chae, Grace (2017) *Complicity or complicity?: Reconsidering the UN Command's role in Syngman Rhee's release of North Korean pows*, *The Journal of American-East Asian relations*, Vol 24 No: 2-3, 128-159

⁷LT Genl Kaul Brij Mohan, (1967) *The Untold Story*, Allied Publishers p 150

⁸ LT Genl Kaul Brij Mohan, (1967) *The Untold Story*, Allied Publishers p 150

Bhagwat Sharan Upadhyay was an internationally renowned scholar. He has written several books on Indian History, Archaeology, Culture and Art. He was a visiting professor of several universities in USA and Europe. He has written his travelogue “Wo Duniya (Those world)” in Hindi which published in 1952. He has written a chapter entitled “Uncle Sam Hansta hai (Uncle Sam Laugh)” which gives his insightful account on Korean War from USA.

Upadhyay wrote “When a city is built, so many plans are laid out, construction begins after testing everything minutely. Buildings, skyscrapers are built, railway tracks are laid beneath the ground. The amount of labour, wealth and mind spent is immense. But One day when I wake from my deep sleep and break everything, destroy everything not even in a day’s time but in within hours.”⁹

He recalls the destruction of WW-II and wrote “If you want to see my dance of fury, ask Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Hiroshima, where not a single person could survive in healthy condition among four hundred thousand of population and those who were left were either turned to be physically or mentally challenged. And Nagasaki, where you can still find in the flames in the base of ruins and people groaning in pain under the ashes of the city. I wanted Bismark and I created one, I wanted Kaiser and I strangulated Bismark to create one and then one Hitler on the body of Kaiser.”¹⁰

4. Conclusion

India was a major player in the peace restoration in the Korean war. India had become independence just before the Korean Crisis started and brought to the United Nations. India supported the non-alignment policy in the settlement of global crisis. India believed that Korean crisis was due to the attitude of the USSR and the US.

According to the former South Korean president Lee Myung-Bak who has made remark in 2010 that Korea was fortunate to have India, the source of an ancient and noble civilization, as a friend during the war. The Ambulance Medical unit headed by Col A. G. Rangaraj valiantly rushed to the aid of wounded soldiers in the face of a fierce crossfire. For its remarkable service, the medical unit received citations of merit from the Korean government on a number of occasions. The devoted service of India during the Korean War has affected the Korean people. Today, the Korean people are appreciating the service provided by India during the Korean war.

Indian accounts of Col Manakampat Kesavan Unnu Nair, Gen Brij Mohan Kaul, Lt Gen Ashoka Banerjee, Bhagwat Sharan Upadhyay, Jagat S Mehta and others provides the bases for the Indian perspectives on Korean war. The authors of the autobiography gave their view through their own mixed experience related to Korean war and peace making and peace-building process. There is relevance of visiting such accounts from Indian perspective as there has been dominant tendency among the Cold War historiographer to presents the narrative of the Korean War with its domineering emphasis on the role of primarily superpowers and bipolarity. In order to obfuscates the role played by non-aligned countries like India for the cause of peace and vision for unified Korea, it is imperative to explore and revisit the Indian accounts of the Korean war, especially, several personalities who were directly engaged in korean peninsula during the crises.

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⁹ Upadhyay Bhagwat Sharan,(1952) Wo Duniya(Those World),Delhi: Alok Publication p 4

¹⁰ Upadhyay Bhagwat Sharan,(1952) Wo Duniya(Those World),Delhi: Alok Publication p 4

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